

Simulation Examples

In order to detect the group targets in the air, an ASC-based unitary matrix pencil method is proposed to estimate the number of group targets in this work. This work lays the foundation for subsequent target detection. The number of three simple model group targets is estimated by simulation software FEKO and MATLAB to verify the effectiveness of our proposed method. The parameters of the three simple models are as follows.

(1) Arbitrary Spheres Array Structure

Ten PEC spheres are randomly constructed in the electromagnetic simulation software FEKO as group targets for detection. The coordinates of these spheres are given in Figure 1. The radius of the PEC sphere is 0.1m. The mesh size is divided according to the twelfth wavelength. The incident frequency is L-band from 1 GHz to 2 GHz, with step of 20 MHz. The auxiliary sources are set as the multiple plane waves from $\theta=100^\circ$, $-3^\circ \leq \varphi \leq 3^\circ$ with $\Delta\varphi=0.5^\circ$. The RCS of group targets is obtained by physical optics (PO) method.

Figure 1. The coordinates of arbitrary ten PEC spheres in free space.

(2) Arbitrary Ball Cones Array Structure

In order to verify that the proposed method in this work is applicable to group targets with different attitudes, the following seven ball cone group targets are taken as examples to compare the estimation accuracy of group targets with the same attitude and different attitudes. Figure 2 shows the model diagram of the ball cone. The bottom radius of this ball cone is 0.25m, the ball head radius is 0.1m and the height is 1.5m. As shown in Figure 3, there are seven ball cones in free space. In Figure 3a, all the ball cones are in the same attitude, that is, in the same direction. In Figure 3b, all the ball cones are in the different attitudes, and their placement spreads around to avoid mutual influence. The incident direction of the plane waves is set to a fixed pitch angle of 100° , and the incident frequency is arbitrary band from 2 GHz to 2.6 GHz with 12 MHz interval. The number of group targets is estimated by the changes of the frequency and azimuth.

Figure 2. The model of a ball cone.

Figure 3. The coordinates of arbitrary seven ball cones in free space. (a) The ball cone group targets in the same attitude; (b) The ball cone group targets in the different attitudes.

(3) Arbitrary Aircrafts Array Structure

Figure 4. The model of an aircraft.

Figure 5. The coordinates of arbitrary five aircrafts in free space.

A slightly complex group target model is discussed in this section in order to further verify the effectiveness of the proposed method. The size of the aircraft model is shown in Figure 4. Figure 5 gives the coordinate of the five aircrafts. The incident wave is a

plane wave of any wave band, ranging from 2 GHz to 2.6 GHz with an interval of 12MHz. The pitch angle is still 100° . Azimuth is any angle range from -15° to -8° with an interval of 0.4° .